

Metal Complexes as Ligands : Binuclear Alkali Metal Complexes with Copper(II)- and Nickel(II)-Salicylaldimines

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The Schiff base complexes of nickel(II) and copper(II)-N,N'-disalicylidene ethylenedimine [M_aES] have been used as a bidentate ligand (complex ligand) in the synthesis of novel binuclear alkali metal complexes of the general formula [$M_aES.M_bL$], M_aES acting as a bidentate complexing agent, coordinating through two phenolic oxygens to alkali metal salts M_bL (where, M_bL = Li, Na or K salts of 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, 8-hydroxyquinoline, anthranilic acid as well as alkali metal salts KSCN, LiCl, NaBr and NaI). The phenolic C-O link retained a considerable amount of partial double bond character in these binuclear complexes. The structure has been substantiated by infrared, electronic spectra and magnetic studies.

In recent years, the formation of oxygen bridged complexes containing two different ligands has become of interest to coordination chemists. Transition metal complexes having phenolic oxygen atoms or β -diketone have been used as a ligand to study oxygen bridged complexes. Since all of these studies involved only transition metals, we thought it of interest to study the same phenomenon with the alkali metals.

As regards the study of alkali metals with due reference to the chances of complex formation, we have selected [*bis*-N,N'-ethylenedis(salicylideneiminato)copper(II)]¹ and [*bis*-N,N'-ethylenedis(salicylideneiminato)nickel(II)]² denoted as CuES and NiES, respectively as 'metal complex' ligands, and studied their behaviour.

The formation of oxygen bridged binuclear complexes from metal salicylaldimines (i.e., CuES or NiES) has been well established by Gruber *et al*³⁻⁵. The CuES or NiES acts as a bidentate ligand in complexing with metal halides, $M'X_2$ (i.e., $CuCl_2$, $NiCl_2$, etc.), to which it coordinates through the two phenolic oxygen atoms. The crystal structure of the compound $(CuES)_2.NaClO_4$ has also been reported by Truter and coworkers⁶ showing attachment of sodium with phenolic oxygen.

In view of the above, it was decided to extend the investigation by a systematic examination of the complexes of CuES and NiES with alkali metal salts (both organic and inorganic), which may be useful in understanding the transport and absorption mechanism of alkali metal ions from soil to plant.

Experimental

Our usual method of synthesis was to take CuES or NiES in a mixture of benzene and absolute ethanol (1 : 1), and to add alkali metal salts to it. The reaction mixture was then refluxed with constant stirring on a hot plate for about 12-16 hr. The whole thing went into solution and subsequently the

adducts were precipitated in hot condition during the process of refluxing. They were filtered, washed with a mixture of benzene and absolute ethanol (1 : 1) and dried in an air oven at 90°.

Results and Discussion

The adducts are insoluble in benzene, ethanol and chloroform. They are stable under dry condition, but decompose on exposure to moisture; as such, they were kept in a desiccator over anhydrous $CaCl_2$. The colour, decomposition temperature and analytical values of these complexes are given in Table 1. Detailed discussions of infrared spectra, magnetic properties and electronic spectra of binuclear alkali metal adducts have been done to establish their structure and bonding.

Infrared spectra :

Infrared spectra were recorded in Nujol mull for the ligands and the complexes between 4000-650 cm^{-1} . Selected absorption bands in different regions are given in Table 1 and Table 2.

The most important feature is that while there are important differences between the infrared spectrum of CuES and NiES and the binuclear complexes formed when they act as ligand, the spectra of the various complexes are essentially the same, being independent of whether a transition or non-transition metal is bound to the complex ligand. The effect of coordination obviously will be the greatest for bands associated with the phenolic oxygen, and progressively less for linkages further from the coordination sites.

Table 2 gives the C=O infrared bands of CuES and NiES together with the binuclear transition metal complexes derived from them. Table 1 gives the C=O infrared bands of binuclear alkali metal complexes derived from CuES and NiES. Comparing the two tables for C=O infrared bands, we arrive at the conclusion that shifting of infrared bands for

TABLE 1

Compounds	Colour	Decomp. Temp. (°C)	% N		% Cu/Ni		% Alkali metal		C=O frequency near 1530 cm ⁻¹	Magnetic moment at 27°
			Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.		
CuES	Green	322							1532	1.90
CuES.Li1N2N	Light green	225	8.41	8.50	12.86	12.48	—	1.37	1538	2.1
CuES.Na1N2N	Yellowish green	228	8.61	8.00	12.40	12.10	4.30	4.38	1538	2.2
CuES.K1N2N	Yellowish green	240	8.00	7.77	11.68	11.74	7.35	7.21	1540	—
CuES.Na8HQ	Brown	250	8.19	8.45	12.39	12.78	4.65	4.65	—	1.91
CuES.K8HQ	Brown	255	7.86	8.19	12.62	12.39	7.63	7.60	1538	2.2
CuES.LiAnth	Violet	240	8.46	8.88	13.37	13.43	—	1.48	1545	1.9
CuES.NaAnth	Violet	242	8.26	8.59	13.41	12.99	4.76	4.70	1542	2.1
CuES.KSCN	Reddish violet	280	8.97	9.86	13.90	14.80	9.22	9.14	1555	1.9
CuES.LiCl	Pink	290	7.12	7.51	16.30	17.06	—	—	1538	2.2
CuES.NaBr	Reddish violet	290	5.88	6.47	14.46	14.68	5.35	5.31	1538	1.9
CuES.NaI	Pink	300	5.32	5.84	13.41	13.24	4.82	4.79	1555	—
NiES	Bright red	330							1536	Diamag.
NiES.Li1N2N	Yellow	255	8.38	8.33	11.89	11.65	—	—	1550	"
NiES.Na1N2N	Yellow	260	8.40	8.08	11.00	11.29	4.51	4.42	1550	"
NiES.K1N2N	Yellow	262	7.26	7.84	11.10	10.95	7.31	7.28	1550	1.62
NiES.NaAnth	Reddish brown	252	8.65	8.68	12.81	12.13	4.80	4.75	1540	1.92
NiES.NaBr	Yellow	280	6.71	6.54	14.30	13.70	5.36	5.38	1543	Diamag.
NiES.NaI	Yellow	275	5.21	5.89	12.86	12.36	4.95	4.84	1550	—

1N2N = 1-Nitroso-2-naphthol
 8HQ = 8-Hydroxyquinoline
 Anth = Anthranilic acid

TABLE 2—POSITION OF THE INFRARED BAND NEAR 1530 cm⁻¹ (ASSIGNED TO C=O STRETCHING FREQUENCY) IN VARIOUS TRANSITION METAL COMPLEXES⁷⁻¹¹

Compound	Frequency (cm ⁻¹)
X = CuES	1532
X.CuCl ₂	1533
X.ZnCl ₂	1551
X ₂ .Cu(ClO ₄) ₂ .3H ₂ O	1556
X ₂ .Ni(ClO ₄) ₂ .3H ₂ O	1554
X ₂ .Mg(ClO ₄) ₂ .3H ₂ O	1555
X ₂ .Sr(ClO ₄) ₂ .1½H ₂ O	1549
X ₂ .Ba(ClO ₄) ₂	1549
X ₂ .AgClO ₄ .2H ₂ O	1544
Y = NiES	1536
Y.CoCl ₂	1556
Y ₂ .Ni(ClO ₄) ₂ .3H ₂ O	1555
Y ₂ .Co(ClO ₄) ₂ .3H ₂ O	1556
Y ₂ .Fe(ClO ₄) ₂ .2H ₂ O	1553
Z = (ZnES) ₂	1552, 1533
Z.ZnCl ₂	1554
Z.ZnCl ₂ .H ₂ O	1538

both transition metal complexes and alkali metal complexes are virtually the same.

In the present complexes and bridged binuclear complexes derived from bidentate salicylaldehyde complexes, 1530 cm⁻¹ band was consistently shifted up by 15-30 cm⁻¹ (Table 1 and Table 2), suggesting that this band may be due to the C=O stretching frequency in these compounds, rather than the C=N. This upward shift is due to the maintenance of a ring current arising out of electron delocalisation in the chelate ring.

Due to the delocalization of electrons towards the benzene ring, the ν(C=O) (phenolic) stretch is expected to occur at higher energy in comparison to the ν(C—O) (alcoholic) stretch¹². It is, therefore, suggestive that the phenolic C—O link attained a

considerable amount of partial double bond character in these complexes. This is what is to be expected from the readiness with which these binuclear complexes were formed.

The above assignments were also found compatible with those made for the C=O links in metalacetylacetonates¹³. This has also been supported by the observation that *bis*-(N-methylsalicylaldehyde)zinc(II), which is known to be dimeric with two bridging and two non-bridging molecules per dimer¹⁴, has a doublet band in this region (1534 and 1553 cm⁻¹).

Magnetic property :

Magnetic measurements were taken on Cahn-Faraday electronic balance at 27°. The results are recorded in Table 1.

The magnetic moment of CuES has been found to be 1.90 B.M., suggesting their square planar structure with coordination number 4. The binuclear alkali metal complexes have magnetic moment values in the range of 1.90–2.24 B.M., suggesting the same geometry of CuES in the alkali metal adducts.

NiES is diamagnetic, suggesting a square planar geometry with a coordination number 4 for Ni²⁺ ion. The binuclear complex compounds of alkali metal salts with NiES are also diamagnetic in nature (except NiES.NaBr and NiES.Na-Anth) suggesting the same stereochemistry of NiES in adducts. The slight deviation from strict diamagnetism in the case of NiES.NaBr and NiES.Na-Anth is generally indicative of one of the types of so called 'anomalous behaviour'.

Had Na.8HQ been attached to NiES through nitrogen of 8HQ and nickel ion, the Ni²⁺ ion would

have assumed 5-coordination stereochemistry. This would have resulted in the formation of a paramagnetic compound. On the other hand, if Na.8HQ had been attached by oxygen and nitrogen atoms of 8HQ (with Na⁺ outside the coordination sphere) to the Ni²⁺ ion, the compound would have been a six coordinated octahedral nickel(II) complex, showing paramagnetism with a μ_{eff} value ~ 3.2 B.M.

The μ_{eff} value for NiES.NaBr and NiES.Na-Anth are 1.92 B.M. and 1.62 B.M., respectively, which are very low compared to 3.4 B.M. We therefore conclude that coordination number of NiES has not been raised even in the case of NiES.NaBr or NiES.Na-Anth.

It is interesting to note that CuES formed complexes with all the three alkali metals (e.g. LiCl, NaBr, NaI and KSCN), while NiES formed only with sodium (i.e. NaBr and NaI). This may be due

to the size of the metal ions and distance of the ligand.

Electronic spectra :

All electronic spectra were recorded on Varian Cary-14 spectrophotometer in Nujol mull.

As a result of the distorted octahedral or square coordination of Cu(II), a detailed interpretation of its electronic absorption spectrum is somewhat complicated. We have not therefore studied the electronic spectra of alkali metal complexes derived from CuES. Study of magnetic properties of the adducts derived from CuES is itself a sufficient evidence to establish the structure of these compounds.

The absorption band of medium intensity at 450 nm in electronic spectra of NiES suggests the square planar structure of Ni²⁺ with the coordination number 4, due to which it is bright red in colour. The absorption band of binuclear alkali metal complexes derived from NiES is found in the range of 450 nm to 500 nm, suggesting the same square planar geometry of NiES with coordination number 4 in all the alkali metal adducts. As the coordination number of Ni²⁺ in NiES remains the same in the adducts, it is clear that alkali metal salts are not attached through Ni²⁺ ion. No absorption band has been found in the range of 600 nm to 1200 nm in the binuclear alkali metal complexes. The absence of these bands in electronic spectra further confirms that the coordination number of Ni²⁺ in NiES binuclear alkali metal complex compounds have not been raised, but remains 4 with square planar geometry.

Structure and bonding :

In the present complexes, the complex ligands have two phenolic oxygens in the *cis* position and are forced to act as bidentate. The bonding between the salicylaldehyde complex M_aES and the alkali metal is most likely to occur by dative bonding via the two phenolic oxygen atoms of the ligand which has been supported by the ir spectra, magnetic properties and electronic spectral studies of the adducts. The structure and bonding of the newly prepared compounds, of the general formula [M_aES. M_bL], may be what is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. M_a = Cu(II) and Ni(II).
M_bL = Alkali metal salts of 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, 8-hydroxyquinoline, anthranilic acid and LiCl, NaBr, NaI and KSCN.

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